

THE ESSENCE OF THE SCIENCE OF SOCIOLOGY IN THE TRAINING OF MILITARY PERSONNEL

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Annotation: The article presents analytical ideas about the relevance of sociology in training specialists of the Armed Forces of New Uzbekistan.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, Armed Forces, spiritual - educational, social and sociological factors.

INTRODUCTION

In today's global world, the science of sociology is not limited to simply recording the major social and political events taking place in the society, but also reveals its true nature and content. The science of sociology is also valuable because of its clarity and concreteness, the fact that the scientific answers to the issues under its responsibility are thoroughly based and repeatedly checked. This science is not limited only to the complete response to the state of current social conditions, but also predicts the level of prospective changes in social conditions. In this respect, it is necessary to thoroughly study the theory, practice and research methods of sociology. Including:

- explaining the initial parts of studying social problems in the development of society from a professional point of view to listeners and cadets.

- it is explained by conveying to the minds of students the methods and methodologies of solving current issues of sociology, sociological analysis and creation of recommendations. The reason is that in today's modern conditions, serious attention is being paid to the priority issues of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. As stated by the President, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "We will consistently continue to create the most favorable conditions for our children to master modern knowledge and skills in the field of education" [1].

It is important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching and to apply new informational and pedagogical technologies for students and cadets to master the science of sociology. Textbooks, educational and methodical manuals, lecture texts, handouts, and electronic materials are used in mastering the subject. Lectures and practical training are conducted on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies in accordance with the subjects of the subject. Of course, the socio-economic, ideological-theoretical conditions for the creation of the science of Sociology, O. Comte - the founder of positive sociology, his initial plans to create sociology as an independent science, encyclopedic scientists of antiquity and social thinkers of the East are in the first place when entering the science. It is necessary to pay attention to the important sources of modern sociology whose teachings (Plato, Aristotle, Farobi, Ibn Khaldun, etc.), the problem of the object and subject of sociology in the works of the classics of Sharab sociology, and the relationship of sociology with other sciences.

In this regard, the theoretical connection of the science of sociology with the science of philosophy, the connection with history, economic theory, ethnography, political science, psychology and other social and humanitarian sciences, the connection of sociology with specific sciences: biology, physics, medicine analyzing the factors affecting the development of this science from the theoretical

side of science, and mathematics and computer science from the practical side, focusing on the concept of structure in science and its importance, its main components. It is necessary to fully analyze the dynamics of the development of its elements. Also, fundamental (main) sociology in the fields and topics of science. Sociological analysis of fundamental problems of society. Theoretical and applied sociology: their commonality and difference. Efforts to develop universal theories in the history of sociology. Creation of empirical sociology and its impact on the development of sociological theory. Special and network directions in sociology. One of the requirements of today's era is the wider research and application of deep thematic concepts such as macrosociology and microsociology. For example, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- concept of society and sociality;
- Eastern thinkers' views on society;
- the definition of sociality in the works of the founders of Western sociology;

Also, in the concept of M. Weber, totalitarian society, its signs and methods of socio-political organization. Society and the state. Description of society in mechanistic, organic and other ways. The concept of society in the theory of T. Parsons, its four-function paradigm. Different definitions of today's society. Traditional society and Industrial society. Their signs. "Abundant society", "Open society", "Closed society", "Consumer society", "Post-industrial society", etc. .

"Representatives of military science also join the ranks of this category of people and make an individual contribution to ensuring defense and security with their research".[2]

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL RELATIONS

Types of social relations: like-mindedness, cooperation, conflicts, struggle, alienation, indifference, crisis, discrimination, inequality. Pluralism in the system of social relations. Basics of social relations.

Consistency, stability and cooperation - as factors of successful functioning of social systems. The concept of consensus in the concept of E. Durkheim.

Cooperation as the main sign of sociality. Stability and crisis consciousness in the sociology of positivism.

Alienation and decline. F.Tennis, M.Weber, G.Zimmel, the founders of existential and phenomenological sociology, their views on the interrelationship of alienation and crisis phenomena in society. Types of alienation and their social consequences. Equality and pluralism as principles of social order. The role of the national idea and national ideology in the system of social relations.

The concept of social development in sociology. The relationship between the concepts of social change and development. Social progress, regression, evolution and revolution as a form of social change.

Problems of social development. Forms of social development: evolutionary, revolutionary and reformist developments. Evolutionary development and its advantages. Social revolutions and their negative consequences. Social reforms and their types. The role of national mentality in the Uzbek development model. Importance of national way of thinking in the experience of developed countries.

As stated by the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy" is an important direction.[3]

The uniqueness of the processes of democratization of state power and management in new Uzbekistan. Global socio-economic recessions and their negative impact on social development processes. The importance of socio-cultural characteristics of Uzbekistan in the development of measures against socio-economic decline.

Sociological research program. Structure of the program: theoretical - methodological and methodical departments. The main elements of the program: defining the problem; determining the purpose and tasks, object and subject of the research; systematic analysis of the object, theoretical and empirical interpretation of concepts, expression of hypotheses; data processing and analysis.

The general classification of data collection methods in sociology is manifested through the following developments: survey, observation, experiment, document study methods, their uniqueness

QUERY METHOD

Types of request. Questionnaire (questionnaire) as a central element of the survey method. Questionnaire making technique. The general structure of the questionnaire. Types of questions in the questionnaire, basic requirements. Verbal inquiry and its features. Interview style. Observation method and its essence. Types of observation. The problem of tracking accuracy and ways to ensure it. Monitoring periods and procedure. Monitoring tools, methods of recording monitoring results.

The Uzbek people are the inheritors of a long and rich history, high culture and spirituality, great ancestors who have gone to the world. Inculcating its history, spiritual values and national traditions in the minds of the young generation, teaching them to live with a sense of justice, honesty, loyalty to the country, courage, protecting the honor and pride of the nation, and concern for the future and prospects of the Motherland is the demand of the times.

Renaissance is not only a European phenomenon. The works of scientists who studied world culture as a whole show that Movarounnahr and Khorasan, which are located in the center of Asia, had a huge cultural uplift several centuries earlier than Italy (IX-XII centuries), science, philosophy, literature developed, and advanced humanitarian ideas occupied the public mind. , intellectual and creative activity flourished.

The history of our country in the Middle Ages shows that the incomparable rise in the fields of culture and education, medicine, literature, art and architecture, the creation of scientific schools, the emergence and coming of age of a wave of new talented generations - all this is primarily the economy of the countries that were formed in our country, was directly related to the rapid growth of rural and urban economy, the high level of development of crafts and trade, the construction

of roads, the opening of new caravan routes and, above all, the provision of relative stability.

Historically, the presence of a developed culture in the life of the peoples of Central Asia is evidenced by the monuments written in ancient Bactrian, Sughd, Urhun, and Khorezm inscriptions, works of mural art and sculptures, and examples of architecture.

The Great Silk Road served as an ancient international transport artery from the II century BC to the XV century AD, connecting regions and countries such as China, India and Central Asia, the Middle and Middle East, and the Mediterranean region. This road served to ensure not only trade relations, but also the exchange of information between continents and countries, in the rapid spread of new technologies and developments (silk, porcelain, gunpowder, paper and many other products), agricultural crops and agrotechnologies, as well as cultural values. played an important role in its development and thus created conditions for inter-civilizational communication and exchange of technologies.

During these times, the people of different countries enriched each other with scientific knowledge and achievements. Through the Great Silk Road, information about the activities of great scholars and thinkers of the Eastern and Western world was transmitted to Europe, and from Europe to Asia. There is a practical opportunity to study the scientific works, ideas and discoveries of Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Ptolemy and other great scholars of antiquity.

The Central Asian region was considered the source of two powerful renaissances that took place in the IX-XII and XIV-XV centuries, and was rightly recognized by the world scientific community as the Eastern Renaissance - Eastern Renaissance, which had a positive effect on the Renaissance processes in other regions of the world.

At the same time, as many researchers have noted, if as a result of the European Renaissance there were new discoveries in literature and art, architectural masterpieces, medicine and human understanding, then the characteristic feature of

the Eastern Renaissance was, first of all, mathematics, astronomy, physics, chemistry, manifested in the development of exact and natural sciences such as geodesy, pharmacology, medicine, as well as history, philosophy and literature.

IX-XII centuries were a period rich in historical and cultural events in the life of our people. It was during this period that great attention was paid to the development of science in the states of the Samanids, Karakhanids, Ghaznavids and Khorezmshahs. In particular, by the 9th century, that is, during the Somonides period, Movarounnahr became a place where the Greek scientific and philosophical school, Arabic geography, Persian history, and Turkestan medical and mathematical schools joined.

In Central Asia in the IX-XII centuries, the creation of a single common space in independent states accelerated the general development. Local states solve the problems of money circulation, trade, cultural, political and external communication within their borders, create a guarantee of security and financial security, and first of all, it is necessary for the uniform prosperity and development of their countries, and in addition, the entire Arab Muslim world. created all the conditions.

It is known that the favorable geographical location, nature, and climate of Central Asia, which is the center of ancient culture, ensured the earlier start of socio-economic development in the region and was a ring that connected the East with Farb, Mesopotamia, Iran, Egypt, later Greece and Rome with China and India, and ensured the crossbreeding of the cultures of different peoples. passes the task.

The formation of independent states in Movarounnahr had a great impact on their political stability, economic development and development of cultural life.

Our cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Urganch and Marv, which have a history of almost three thousand years and have been a crossroads of world civilization and culture of different peoples, have been formed and developed as centers of science and culture. For example, along with Rome, Samarkand, whose

blue domes attract millions of tourists, has gained worldwide fame under the name of "eternal city, ancient Bukhara" - Qubbatul-Islam.

The political unity, economic and spiritual needs created in the centralized states that operated in Central Asia in the IX-XII centuries, as well as the wide development of trade, economic and cultural relations with foreign countries through the Great Silk Road contributed to the development of construction, architecture, literature and art, crafts, science and religion in our country. created favorable conditions.

In the IX-XII centuries, the growth of the state's position gave impetus to the improvement of the economic situation. The elimination of the threat of nomad invasion, stability, high farming culture, handicrafts and other sectors have stimulated the development of the economy. The geographical location of Central Asia and trade relations along the Great Silk Road had a great impact not only on the economic, but also on the exchange of scientific and cultural experience (between the East and the West). The development of international relations through the Great Silk Road has become of great importance.

Spiritual values that have existed in Central Asia for thousands of years have been formed on the basis of contacts between different religions and peoples. Central Asia is the only region where all world religions (Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Judaism, Islam) are spread. During this period, Islam became the ideology of the state and society, became the center of the Islamic religion and culture of our country, the place where jurisprudence, law, mysticism developed. In the countries of Central Asia, rulers patronized and guided representatives of Islamic religion, science and culture. On their part, they served the development of science and culture in the country.

Our youth cannot achieve new and higher goals in science and other fields without deep assimilation of the knowledge gained in the field of science, including the universal discoveries made in the Middle Ages in the East. Today, the thoughts and aspirations of our youth have changed fundamentally, their political level and

legal culture are rising, and they are moving forward towards a clear goal, which will be a solid foundation for the achievements we have achieved and will achieve in the future. In the present era, new global problems are emerging before humanity. Climate change, depletion of natural resources and other environmental problems should be mentioned among them. Solving these problems requires comprehensive growth of intellectual capacity, re-perception and new evaluation of the laws that have been created for many centuries, conducting deep scientific research and experiments on the large-scale study of the existence that surrounds us.

We all know that life never stands still, it is always moving forward with intensity and rapid pace. Whoever does not keep up with the pace of life's development, looks at it indifferently and indifferently, is enamored with his achievements, indulges in a mood of calmness and airiness, without a doubt, will remain at one end of the rapidly changing history, backwardness and dreams. This is the cruel, bitter truth of life and we must never forget it. We must not forget that we live in the era of globalization and the Internet, and that progress never stands still. Therefore, living proud of the achievements of the past alone will not ensure the great future of Uzbekistan. Maybe our youth must live with the concept and aspiration of "What will I leave to the next generation?" Along with further development of our achievements, we should strive to surpass others.

Today, our young people who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, who think independently and in a new way, who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country, are the foundation of our future. It is necessary for our youth to become active participants in building a democratic, civil society. We must educate them in the spirit of high spirituality and historical memory, living on the basis of the rule of law, loyalty to the country, and justice. For this purpose, today the state has strengthened the rights and freedoms of young people to get education, choose a profession, become an owner, engage in private entrepreneurship, small and medium business, participate in political processes and other rights and freedoms in the Constitution and laws.

The legacy of our great ancestors, who made an invaluable contribution to the development of our history and world civilization, is the solid foundation of our independence today. This heritage plays a major role in educating our youth in the spirit of national ideals, national ideology, love for the Motherland, loyalty, and pride.

THE METHOD OF STUDYING DOCUMENTS

Concept of document in sociology, its types. The problem of reliability of documents as a source of information. Types of document analysis. Content analysis as a type of document study method. Experimental method. Types of experiments. The structure of social experiment, its cognitive possibilities. Selection of object, formation of experimental and control groups, experimental situation, analysis of results. Instructions and recommendations on the organization of seminar classes are developed by the professors of the department. It recommends strengthening knowledge based on textbooks and methodological manuals, using handouts, increasing the knowledge of students and trainees by publishing scientific articles and theses, and preparing visual educational tools on topics. During the seminar, the cadets and trainees will strengthen their knowledge, skills and competences on the topics covered in a practical way. Now, our country is entering a new stage of development based on the principle "From national revival to national rise". As the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "Today, when our country is being talked about on a global scale, the phrase ``New Uzbekistan" is mentioned. This is a recognition that we have stepped into a completely new stage of development in recent years, and that we are making great progress"[4].

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, we put forward the following recommendations, including: as the principle, position, tactics and strategy are of great importance in the processes of social integration of the whole world in the military education system, we must first of all deeply understand that this science is a scientific study of man and society.

Therefore, it is appropriate to teach at all Temurbek schools and higher military educational institutions. Because by teaching this subject, it will be possible to prepare intellectually mature specialists in New Uzbekistan. The New Uzbekistan - 2030 strategy will be based on the above ideas.

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